

**Intercultural Communication Competence: Blazing Need in a
Multicultural Environment**

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Synopsis

How shall I talk of the sea to the frog,
if it has never left his pond?
How shall I talk of the frost to the bird of the summerland,
if it has never left the land of its birth?
How shall I talk of life with the sage,
if he is prisoner of his doctrine?

- *Chung Tsu, 4th Century B.C.*

The world is shrinking. People of different cultural backgrounds are more interdependent than ever. The 21st century confronts ever-shifting social, cultural, and technological challenges. The rapid development in every aspect of the 21st century requires that we see things through others' eyes and develop a new way of living together. This global mindset can only result from competent intercommunication among people from diverse cultures. *Thus, the need for intercultural communication enhancement across disciplines becomes critical for success in our world.*

The need for intercultural communication enhancement, especially intercultural sensitivity, across disciplines becomes critical for future success. In view of various issues pertaining to a theme, this paper focus on the need for intercultural communication, issues/examples in MNCs pertaining to intercultural communication and various strategies/models to resolve the bottlenecks of multicultural communication. The study is based on literature review and secondary data.

Key Words: Intercultural Communication, Competence, Multinational Corporations (MNCs)

Intercultural Communication: Concept

Intercultural communication in its most basic form refers to an academic field of study and research. It seeks to understand how people from different countries and cultures behave, communicate and perceive the world around them. The findings of such academic research are then applied to 'real life' situations such as how to create cultural synergy between people from different cultures within a business or how psychologists understand their patients.

The definition of intercultural communication must also include strands of the field that contribute to it such as

- Anthropology,
- Cultural studies,
- Psychology and communication.

There are many researchers and academics of note within the intercultural field, who naturally all have different definitions of 'intercultural communication'. For example *"Intercultural communication,' can...be defined as the interpersonal interaction between members of different groups, which differ from each other in respect of the knowledge shared by their members and in respect of their linguistic forms of symbolic behavior"*¹

The theories developed by the researchers and academics can and has been applied to many fields such as business, management, marketing, advertising and website design. As business becomes more and more international, many companies need to know how best to structure their companies, manage staff and communicate with customers. Intercultural communication gives them an insight into the areas they need to address or understand. Intercultural communication theories are now also used within the education, health care and other public services due to growing multicultural populations.

Even when two people speak a common language, and share common experiences and background knowledge and traditions, the communication process may not work as effectively as we would like. When we add the extra dimension of cultural difference, the

¹ Defined by Karlfried Knapp

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process becomes even more complex. There is an even greater chance of communication breaking down not only because of the language complications, but also because of cultural differences.

"Intercultural communication,' can...be defined as the interpersonal interaction between members of different groups, which differ from each other in respect of the knowledge shared by their members and in respect of their linguistic forms of symbolic behavior"

When people cross cultural boundaries they take their "taken for granted" meaning structure from their home culture. They continue to choose actions consistent with the way they've been enculturated and continue to interpret actions in terms of their own enculturation. It is inevitable that communication across cultural boundaries will break down unless people can recognize their ethnocentrism and take action to overcome it. They must recognize that one culture cannot be judged by the standards of another. This is cultural relativism and it is important to understand this concept and not judge others according to your values. The following diagram², ably sums up those aspects of culture of which one should be aware. (See Diagram 1)

²Given by Courtesy Robin Julian, Monte Sant Angelo College 1999

Intercultural communication competence

Intercultural communication competence is the ability for successful communication with people of other cultures. This ability can be existing already, or be developed and improved thanks to willpower and competence. The bases for a successful intercultural communication are emotional competence, together with intercultural sensitivity.

Cultures can be different not only between continents or nations, but also within the same company or even family: every human being has his own history, his own life and therefore also (in a certain extent) his own culture resp. cultural affiliation (geographical, ethnical, moral, ethical, religious, political, historical).

Basic needs are sensitivity and self-consciousness: the understanding of other behaviors and ways of thinking as well as the ability to express one's own point of view in a transparent way with the aim to be understood and respected by staying flexible where this is possible, and being clear where this is necessary.

It is a balance, situatively adapted, between three parts:

- 1) knowledge (about other cultures, people, nations, behaviors...),
- 2) empathy (understanding feelings and needs of other people), and
- 3) self-confidence (knowing what I want, my strengths and weaknesses, emotional stability).

For assessment of intercultural competence as an existing ability and / or the potential to develop it (with conditions and timeframe), the following characteristics are tested and observed: ambiguity tolerance, openness to contacts, flexibility in behaviour, emotional stability, motivation to perform, empathy, metacommunicative competence, polycentrism.

Need for Intercultural Communication In Multicultural Environment

The following points pose the need for intercultural communication in multicultural environment.

1) Open Business Place

Today's world is undergoing rapid change. Trade barriers are collapsing around the globe, and companies are marketing their products and/or services worldwide. Consequently, business procedures and company structures are adapting to these changes, too. Generally, the term globalization assumes that the whole world has become one market open to all; it also considers the fact that global communication and travel times have shrunk. 1982 John Naisbett pointed out in *Megatrends* national economies have merged into a global economy. Today, economists confirm that "we are in an era of global business - a one world market."³ Marshall Mc Luhan went a step further, calling today's world a global *village* "because of the rapid expansion of worldwide communication networks."⁴As corporations integrate and standardize their organization and operation across the world, they must also learn to be responsive to local cultural differences.

2) Making International Remote Teams Work

³ Brake et al (1995), p. 2.

⁴ Gudykunst and Kim (1984), p. 3.

International companies are geographically and culturally dispersed. In some cases, the importance of a company's original zone of activity has been economically outweighed. Powerful sub-groups have emerged, their results heavily influencing strategic decisions. Using their difference as an advantage, these groups often deeply altered the internal balance of power. This evolution, a consequence of internationalization, has in turn generated the structural evolutions we have been experiencing since the mid-eighties: Creation of lines of products, of divisions by activity, all international.

Brutally, the mono-cultural, ethnocentric logic that prevailed within the zones is shattered. Confused managers now have to find their ways through the complexities of three interacting and potentially conflicting cultural levels – national-inter-national, corporate and functional. They have to deal directly with distant, unknown and different counterparts who are also desperately trying to survive the torments of such complex structures. Therefore, knowing the other person and understanding his or her culture, values and behaviors, becomes a considerable advantage⁵.

3) Stereotyping and Intercultural Issues

A common observation people make about intercultural awareness is that it stereotypes people. The fact that intercultural aspects presents information on a particular nationality or culture is taken to be a negative or positive attribute, i.e. that we box people with rigid labels that correlate to their behavior, values or actions. Such observations are misplaced and misinterpreted.

Intercultural aspects do provide conclusions on cultures or nationalities but it does not stereotype. Stereotyping is usually a negative statement about a group of people. A stereotype emerges when a blanket perception is applied to an entire group of people. For example, we may know one Japanese person who is very quiet so we conclude that all Japanese are quiet and reserved. Or we see certain media images and conclude that because a person is Muslim they are prone to violence and aggression against non-Muslims. Both are far from the truth. Again, a positive stereotype is where we use a blanket expression for a whole people, i.e. all the Chinese are great at mathematics, all Germans are well organized or all English people

⁵ [http://www.kwintessential.co.uk/Cross Cultural Communication\Managing the Challenges of Intercultural Communication in Teams.html](http://www.kwintessential.co.uk/Cross%20Cultural%20Communication\Managing%20the%20Challenges%20of%20Intercultural%20Communication%20in%20Teams.html)

are well mannered. Although the intent behind the statement is positive, it still does not reflect the truth.

In conclusion, intercultural understanding does not stereotype people but provides platform to work with different cultures. These generalizations are based upon careful research and observation and offer people with simple guidelines on a country or culture. These guidelines simply act as an intercultural safety net people can turn to when uncertain.

Factors forced MNCs for Intercultural Communication: Open Business Place, Making International Remote Teams Work, Stereotyping and Intercultural Issues, Language and Culture, Language and Culture, The Spoken Word, The Written Word, Communication Channels, Public Relation Materials

4) Language and Culture

In order for a PR⁶ campaign to be successful abroad, an appreciation of the target language and its cultural nuances is necessary. The PR and advertising industries are littered with examples of poor translations and a lack of cross-cultural understanding leading to PR failure. For example, when Ford launched the ‘Pinto’ in Brazil they were puzzled as to why sales were dead. Fortunately they found out that Brazilians did not want to be seen driving a car meaning ‘small male genitals’ and promptly changed the name.

Translation of documents, slogans and literature must be checked and double-checked for meanings and cross-cultural nuances. This should not only take place between languages but also within languages. Even in English there are cross-cultural differences in meanings.

5) The Spoken Word

⁶ PR stands for Public Relations

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Areas where the spoken word is used in PR, such as press conferences or interviews, should be prepared for within a cross-cultural framework. In short, speaking styles and the content used differs across cultures.

British and American communication styles are described as 'explicit', meaning messages are conveyed solely through words. Correlating background information is deemed necessary and divulged, ambiguity is avoided and spoken words have literal meaning. In many other cultures, communication is 'implicit'. The message listeners are likely to interpret is based on factors such as who is speaking, the context and non-verbal cues. Spoken words do not fully convey the whole story as listeners are expected to read between the lines.

With relation to content, speakers must be aware of the cross-cultural differences in humor, metaphors, aphorisms and anecdotes. In addition, references to topics such as politics and/or religion can be a very sensitive issue in other cultures. When the spoken word is used the cross-cultural distinctions of the target culture must be incorporated in order to help the speaker appeal to and identify with the audience.

6) The Written Word

Press releases, features and copywriting all require a certain amount of cross-cultural sensitivity when being applied abroad. Journalistic traditions, writing styles, news worthiness, delivery systems and whether a 'free press' exists are all areas that will affect how the written word is tailored.

In addition, the most important point, from a cross-cultural perspective, is how to write in a way that engages the readers in that society or culture. Some cultures may prefer colorful and inspirational writing, others factual and objective. Some may be motivated by language that incorporates a religious or moral tone, others by a money-orientated or materialistic one.

When writing, the first step should always be to look at and integrate the cross-cultural particulars of the target audience.

7) Communication Channels

PR practitioners employ many different communication channels when trying to circulate information relating to their campaign. The main channels of communication in the UK or America are the radio, the press, TV, internet and public spaces. However, these channels may not always be applicable abroad.

In many countries the radio, TV or newspapers may not be the primary source of information. Literacy rates may be poor and/or radios may be expensive. In Africa, only 1.4% of the populations have access to the internet⁷. Even where such channels of communication do exist, such as TV, some methods used by PR practitioners, namely guerrilla marketing, would be interpreted differently in foreign countries. For example, interrupting live TV may be laughed at in the UK but in other countries it would be seen as irresponsible and rebellious.

The usual channels of communication in some countries would simply have no effect in terms of PR. In such countries, local alternatives need to be sought such as religious leaders, tribal chiefs, school teachers or NGO's. Information coming from such figures will not only reach the audience but be perceived as more credible than if it were from foreigners.

8) Public Relation Materials

The use of publicity materials in PR campaigns such as logos, slogans, pictures, colors and designs must all be cross culturally examined. Pictures of seemingly innocuous things in one culture could mean something different in another. For example, a company advertised eyeglasses in Thailand by featuring a variety of cute animals wearing glasses. The ad failed as animals are considered to be a low form of life in Thailand and no self-respecting Thai would wear anything worn by animals. Similarly, logos or symbols are culturally sensitive. A soft drink was introduced into Arab countries with an attractive label that had a six-pointed star on it. The Arabs interpreted this as pro-Israeli and refused to buy it.

The above cited areas are but a few of those that require decent cross cultural communication assessment by business community if they wish their international and cross cultural business to succeed. The aim of implementing a cross-cultural communication analysis is to build

⁷ <http://www.kwintessential.co.uk/cultural-services/articles/cross-cultural-pr.html>

sales and market that target the audience as best as possible, meaning appealing to their world-view while avoiding offense.

Intercultural Communication Issues/Examples in MNCs

The companies would need to study and consider all the necessary cultural, social and technical requirements as well as the other environmental regulations of the nation or market in order to determine if the product needs to be adapted to the new market or even in existing market. However, one vital factor is often ignored altogether in the preparation phase: The cultural factor. Failure to consider the cultural factor can lead to failure of the planned international business venture since culture influences consumer behavior (Samovar et al 1999). But this is not just a problem for first timers or companies lacking international experience. It even affects large international corporations as the experiences of BMW & Rover as well as Daimler & Chrysler so aptly demonstrate (Gibson 2007).

A disregard for intercultural communicative skills can cause miscommunication, which can produce misunderstandings that will lead to mistakes. And many mistakes have been made. This is probably due to the fact that “(m)any . . . think that the research they did at home will work abroad or that no market research is needed.”⁸ But “no company can afford to neglect the cultural context of doing business, and no manager has the luxury of ignoring cultural differences.”⁹ The following examples of past marketing mistakes illustrate various levels of miscommunication:

On the *verbal level*, an example of miscommunication is GM’s attempt to sell its popular midsize car, the Chevy Nova, in Mexico in 1970. It took GM a while to discover why it had sales problems. No one realized that the culprit was the car’s name: *no va* means *no go* in Spanish.¹⁰

But misunderstandings can also occur at a *symbolic level*. For example, “the Wise Corporation would have to change or modify its trademark if it decided to test market potato

⁸ Valentine (1989), p. 54.

⁹ Brake et al (1995), p. 31.

¹⁰ Bonvillian and Nowlin (1994), p. 46.

chips in India. The owl, which is the Wise trademark, is a symbol of bad luck in India even though in America it is associated with intelligence.”¹¹

Some companies were surprised to discover that even the *sense of taste* can vary between two otherwise very similar markets. Coca Cola, for example, stumbled on this taste difference when it tried to introduce Cherry Coke to the German market in the 1980’s. The German consumers did not like it, and Coca Cola quickly removed Cherry Coke from the shelves. In 1996 Coca Cola reintroduced Cherry Coke in Germany, but with a different taste more suited for German consumers.¹²

Even assumed *preferences* can be misunderstood. In 1974 VW built an autoplant in Westmoreland, PA, to produce the Rabbit GTI. VW toted the new Pennsylvania built Rabbit as an American built small car, assuming that was what the American consumer wanted. The company recorded massive losses and had to close the plant in 1985. It turned out that the American consumer wanted a German engineered *and* built Volkswagen, not another little American car.¹³

Differences in *shopping behavior* can have an impact on refrigerator sales as Electrolux discovered. It turns out that Northern Europeans want very large refrigerators because they only shop once a week in supermarkets, and they like their freezers on the bottom of the fridge. Southern Europeans, in contrast, want small refrigerators because they shop very regularly in street markets, and they like their freezers on the top.¹⁴

Business ventures often do not fail because of a “lack of money or technology, but rather [due] to the cultural difference and misunderstanding of values of the other person, company, or culture.”¹⁵ Effective business communications, therefore, involves finding the right words and symbols, detecting the right taste, and being aware of local preferences and behaviors. It is, therefore, not only necessary to think globally, but also to act locally and to integrate with the respective target culture.

¹¹ Bonvillian and Nowlin (1994), p. 46.

¹² Ms. Hülsken at Coca Cola Germany, Essen, provided this information on 17 February, 1998.

¹³ The VW Rabbit GTI was built in Westmoreland between 1979 and 1984. This information was conveyed viaphone to Ms. Jamina Bartusch by Ms. Steffi Gründel of VW Wolfsburg on 20 February, 1998.

¹⁴ Brake et al (1995), p. 154.

¹⁵ Elashmawi and Harris (1993), p. 48.

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The importance of heeding different behavioral and cultural patterns is best illustrated by Procter & Gamble's entry to the Japanese market in 1973. By 1987 the company had lost US\$ 200 million. But by June 30, 1990, it had turned the loss into a profit of US\$ 1 billion per annum. This remarkable turnaround came about after Procter & Gamble had integrated and learned to:¹⁶

- know the customer's habits, biases and attitudes;
- tailor its products to the market;
- be sensitive to cultural differences;
- the distribution system;
- and sell the company as well as the brands.

Some companies have, therefore, realized that an ignorance of, or disrespect for cultural differences as well as a lack of effective intercultural communication can lead to losses. Hence, many businesses have recognized the importance of intercultural communication. For the "imposition of universal products, services, and management styles may simply lead to confusion and resistance. We have to learn to communicate in ways that can derive value from differences, not that assume similarity or impose conformity."¹⁷ Consequently, "*at the very least* [emphasis added], all . . . materials require a local editor to interpret the content, and determine its cultural appropriateness."¹⁸ Yet many business managers still believe that just the ability to speak a foreign language grammatically correct is all that is required for effective intercultural communication.¹⁹

Euro Disney: Intercultural Communication²⁰

Any company involved in international business must consider the complexities of intercultural communication. It is essential to know your potential customer, and understand their cultural influences, before you can make them your actual customer. Failing to understand differences between you and your foreign partner can doom your business deal before it even gets started.

¹⁶ Brake et al (1995), p. 29.

¹⁷ Brake et al (1995), p. 150.

¹⁸ Elashmawi and Harris (1993), p. 142.

¹⁹ Brunner (1997), n.p.

²⁰ http://www.exportvirginia.org/FastFacts_2005/FF%20Issues%20Intercultural%20Communication.pdf

EuroDisney²¹ offers an example of the importance of intercultural communication. Because Disney was so successful opening theme parks in Japan and the U.S., it assumed that building a EuroDisney theme park would be just as easy and successful. It turned out that Disney made some key “cultural” errors. The problems began before any buildings were even built. Disney offended the French by using lawyers to negotiate construction and other contacts.

In France, lawyers are only used as a last resort in negotiations, so this implied mistrust on Disney’s part. Disney also instituted a strict dress code for employees based on the U.S. parks dress code.

However, rules about facial hair, fingernail length and appearance were perceived as an attack on French style and culture. Disney’s mistakes not only offended the French people, they reduced potential profits. Disney assumed that Europeans would not eat sit-down breakfasts, which is true in their everyday life. However, Europeans on vacation do enjoy sit-down breakfasts. This mistake led to crowded dining rooms and unhappy customers. Disney also followed U.S. norms and banned the sale of alcohol at the theme park. This was an insult in a country where the consumption of wine with a meal is the way of life. Disney had counted on souvenirs in France selling as well as they had in Japan and the U.S. but Europeans are not as prone to such spending sprees while on vacation.

Fortunately, Disney made the cultural adjustments that were necessary and EuroDisney is doing much better today than when it first started.²²

The Need For Intercultural Communication Training²³

Kim and Paulk (1994) analyze the difficulties experienced between Japanese and American co-worker in an American subsidiary of a large Japanese multinational organization. The main issues were summarized under three categories: language and communication; work style /orientation; and management style/orientation. Apart from problems caused by the

²¹ It started in 1987 when a partnership between the French authorities and The Walt Disney Company was forged to bring Disney magic to the heart of Europe.

²² Mitchell pp.2-3

²³ Peter Hartley & Clive G. Bruckmann pp. 50

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Japanese managers' difficulties with the English language and the 'rapid American speech, major language and communication difficulties included the following:

- The American complained that the Japanese 'lacked verbal clarity, major whereas the Japanese complained that the Americans "lacked intuitive understand.
- The American complained that the Japanese 'gave vague and specific instruction' whereas the Japanese complained that the Americans "needed exact and detail instruction
- The American complained that the Japanese 'Relied on written communication'

All these difficulties represent different cultural perspectives and approach to communication. Both group commented on their efforts and strategies to understand the others perspective although Kim and Paulk comment that the problems 'have not been addressed seriously by the company leadership despite the considerable evidence that 'intercultural strain can be reduced through effective language and cultural instruction'

This type of research raises many questions for multinational organization, including the following:

- Are they aware of the effect of cultural differences?
- Do they understand the experience of the cultural minority person?
- Do they know enough about inter cultural training?

Intercultural Communications strategies/Models

The globalization process is forcing businesses to rethink their strategies. Intercultural communication, skills assume an ever-larger role in global marketing and sale strategies. Consequently, language programs need to respond to these changes. Future business managers must acquire effective intercultural competence. The one world market has forced businesses to think global, act local, and integrate. Intercultural communication serves a vital role in that it can forestall miscommunication, prevent misunderstandings, and avert

mistakes. Here are a few strategies that managers can adapt to promote and improve intercultural communication within and outside their organizations as they operate in a global village:

Many programs are interdisciplinary in nature and are based on various intercultural communication strategies, such programs include: cognitive (intellectual, classroom) model, self-awareness and cultural awareness models, simulation model, and interactional model. Using these models MNCs can achieve intercultural communication competence.

The *cognitive* (intellectual, classroom) strategy promotes understanding of cultural differences and similarities. It helps participants to get more information about a culture. Educators in various intercultural training programs most commonly use this model. As the emphasis is laid on cognitive understanding of customs, values, people, geography, and habits of a specific culture, the normally applied methods of teaching are lectures, films, readings, and different kinds of presentations.

This model, however, has its limitations. It only teaches participants "what to learn" but not "how to learn", teaches them to gain knowledge of a culture without knowing how to perform and adapt behaviorally to it (Chen & Starosta, 1998 : 263). This model cannot guarantee success at living or working in a new culture.

The *self-awareness* training helps participants identify attitudes, opinions and biases embedded in their own culture that influence the way they communicate. The emphasis in this model is laid on understanding oneself as a cultural being. Working in groups the participants learn how their own behaviors influence others and what psychological forces operate in groups.

The limitation of this model is its ethnocentric orientation. Although self-awareness is important for being effective in intercultural communication, its focus on the internalized processes of an individual cannot adequately teach participants about factors involved in cultural interaction (Chen & Starosta, 1998 : 265).

The *cultural awareness* training requires participants to understand the aspects of culture that are universal and specific. It assumes that in order to successfully interact with people from

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other cultures we have to understand our own and others" cultural norms, customs and social systems. The cultural awareness model aims to teach participants to overcome ethnocentrism, to help them understand that our own cultural identity is only one possibility among numerous others. This training model is very popular among Russian educators as it is built on a strong theoretical base. Another strong point of this model is that the participants can reach not only intellectual understanding but also an affective tolerance of cultural differences in the process of intercultural communication (Bennett, 1986).

This training model also has its limitations. First, it may be difficult for the trainees to apply general knowledge in dealing with a specific cultural task; second, in comparing their own culture to others the participants may neglect similarities and exaggerate differences; third, to become thoroughly aware of one's own culture as the base for understanding others is a complex process and may take a long time.

The *simulation* training focuses on the affective and experiential processes of training participants by involving them in an environment that closely resembles a specific culture. (Chen & Starosta, 1998 : 264). The basic assumption of this model is that it is very important for trainees to gain a personal experience in living in a place resembling the host culture, to develop a set of new behaviors and attitudes that will enable them to better adjust to the foreign culture. The main advantage of this model is a strong focus on the participant rather than on the trainer. It is a trial-and-error process, through which participants acquire intercultural communication skills.

However, the simulation model is not widely used by MNCs for several reasons. First, it is difficult to simulate overseas environment; second, it is impossible to gain extensive cultural knowledge through personal experience in a limited time. Commonly, if possible, the simulation model is used as a complementary part of the classroom (cognitive) model.

The *interactional* training presupposes face-to-face interaction with the host/foreign nationals. Through the experiential learning process participants are supposed to figure out the value systems and appropriate behavioral patterns of the host culture. The model is commonly applied to the intercultural workshop programs held on college campuses. As any other model, interactional model also has its advantages and disadvantages.

Many scholars and trainers argue that applying a single model of intercultural training may not sufficiently prepare participants to function properly and effectively in a new cultural environment (Chen & Starosta, 1998 : 267). Better results may be achieved through a combination of several training models.

Moreover, a more effective outcome may be achieved by devising specific training techniques: case studies, critical-incident case studies based on real-life experience of the learners, cultural assimilators, simulations, role playing, team projects, experiential learning, etc.

In sum, effective intercultural communication training can increase the workforces' capacity for intercultural awareness, intercultural sensitivity, and intercultural competence, thus enabling him or her to function effectively in intercultural context.

Conclusion

Globalization creates a world in which an increasing number of people are moving between countries for overseas work or business. A major challenge that expatriates workers and international companies face is how to function successfully in a new cultural environment, in a country with different values, sociocultural rules and norms of behavior.

It is revealed that success or effectiveness in intercultural interaction depends to a large extent on the degree of intercultural competence a person possesses. To function effectively in intercultural context one must have sufficient skills and knowledge to accomplish his job, must be able to adjust properly in a new culture or multicultural environment, and be able to establish interpersonal relations with co-workers and within the culturally differing markets and community. Thus, intercultural communication competence helps not only to survive but also achieve success in an increasingly interdependent global market place and society.

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